

T-pure Fuzzy Ideals and prime Fuzzy Ideals

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Abstract. In this paper, the concepts t-pure fuzzy ideals and prime fuzzy ideals have been investigated. Several basic results related to these concepts have been given and studied. The relationship between them has also been given.

1. Introduzione

The present paper introduces and studies t-pure fuzzy ideals and prime fuzzy ideals. In section one, some basic definitions and results are recalled which will be needed later. In section two, several results about t-pure fuzzy ideals of a fuzzy ring, are given which are necessary in proving some results in the following sections. Section three is devoted for studying prime fuzzy ideals of a fuzzy ring, are given which are necessary in proving some results in the following sections. Its relationship with t-pure fuzzy ideal is also given. Throughout this paper R is commutative ring with unity, and every fuzzy ideal A of a fuzzy ring X is a finite valued, that is $\text{Im}(A)$ is finite set. Finally, $A(0) = X(0)$, for any fuzzy ideal A of a fuzzy ring X .

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S . 1 BASIC CONCEPT:

This section contains some definitions ,Lemmas and properties of fuzzy subset, fuzzy ring, fuzzy ideal which we will be used in the next section .

PRELIMINARY CONCEPTS

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a commutative ring with identity. A **fuzzy subset of R** is a function from R into $[0,1], ([1],[2])$.

Let A and B be fuzzy subset of R. We write $A \subseteq B$ if $A(x) \leq B(x)$ for all $x \in R$. If $A \subseteq B$ and there exists $x \in R$ such that $A(x) < B(x)$, then we write $A \subset B$ and we say that A is a proper fuzzy subset of B, [1]. Note that $A = B$ if and only if $A(x) = B(x)$, for all $x \in R$, [3].

We let $\text{Im}(A)$ denote **the image of A**. We say that A is a finite – valued if $\text{Im}(A)$ is finite, ([1],[4]). $|\text{Im}(A)|$ denote **the cardinality of Im(A)**, [4].

For each $t \in [0,1]$, the set $A_t = \{x \in R \mid A(x) \geq t\}$ is called **a level subset of R** and the set $A^* = \{x \in R \mid A(x) = A(0)\}$, ([1],[4]).

Let $f: R \rightarrow R'$, A and B be two fuzzy subsets of R and R' respectively ,the fuzzy subset $f(A)$ of R' defined by : $f(A)(y) = \sup A(y)$ if $f(y) \neq 0$, $y \in R'$ and $f(A)(y) = 0$, otherwise .It is called **the image of A under f** and denoted by $f(A)$. The fuzzy subset $f^{-1}(B)$ of R defined by : $f^{-1}(B)(y) = B(f(x))$, for all $x \in R$. Is called **the inverse image of B** and denoted by $f^{-1}(B)$, [2].

Let R ,R' be any sets and $f: R \rightarrow R'$ be any function .A fuzzy subset A of R is called **f-invariant** if $f(x) = f(y)$ implies $A(x) = A(y)$, where $x, y \in R$, [3].

Let $x \in R$ and $t \in [0,1]$, let x_t denote the fuzzy subset of R defined by $x_t(y) = 0$ if $x \neq y$ and $x_t(y) = t$ if $x = y$ for all $y \in R$. x_t is called **a fuzzy singleton**, [4].

If x_t and y_s are fuzzy singletons, then $x_t + y_s = (x + y)_\lambda$ and $x_t \circ y_s = (x \cdot y)_\lambda$ where $\lambda = \min \{t, s\}$, ([3],[4]).

Let $I^R = \{A_i \mid i \in \Lambda\}$ be a collection of fuzzy subset of R. Define the fuzzy subset of R (**intersection**) by $(\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} A_i)(x) = \inf \{A_i(x) \mid i \in \Lambda\}$ for all $x \in R$, ([2],[4]).

Let ϕ denote $\phi(x) = 0$ for all $x \in R$, **the empty fuzzy subset** of R, ([3],[5]). Note that throughout our work any fuzzy subset is a nonempty fuzzy subset.

Let A and B be a fuzzy subsets of R, **the product** $A \circ B$ define by $A \circ B(x) = \sup \{A(y)$,

$B(z) \mid x = y \cdot z \}$ $y, z \in R$, for all $x \in R$.

The addition $A + B$ define by $(A + B)(x) = \sup \{ \min \{A(y), B(z) \mid x = y + z\} \mid y, z \in R \}$, for all $x \in R$, [5] .

Let A be a fuzzy subset of R , A is called a **fuzzy subgroup** of R if for all $x, y \in R$, $A(x + y) \geq \min \{A(x), A(y)\}$ and $A(x) = A(-x)$, [5] .

Let A be a fuzzy subset of R , A is called a **fuzzy ring of R** if for all $x, y \in R$,

$A(x - y) \geq \min \{A(x), A(y)\}$ and $A(x \cdot y) \geq \min \{A(x), A(y)\}$ ([1],[5]).

A fuzzy subset A of R is called a **fuzzy ideal of R** if and only if for all $x, y \in R$, $A(x - y) \geq \min \{A(x), A(y)\}$ and $A(x \cdot y) \geq \max \{A(x), A(y)\}$ ([1],[5]).

Let X be a fuzzy ring of R and A be a fuzzy ideal of R such that $A \subseteq X$. Then A is a **fuzzy ideal of the fuzzy ring X** [6]. And A is a **fuzzy ideal of the fuzzy ring X** of R if $A(b-c) \geq \min \{A(b), A(c)\}$ and $A(bc) \geq \min \{ \max \{A(b), A(c)\}, Xbc \}$, ([6],[7]).

Let A be a fuzzy ideal of R . If for all $t \in [0, A(0)]$, then A_t is an ideal of R and A^* is an ideal of R ([1],[4],[7]).

Let $\{A_i \mid i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of fuzzy ideals of R . Then $\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} A_i$ is a fuzzy ideal of R [8].

Let A and B are fuzzy ideals of R , then $A \circ B$ is a fuzzy ideal of R .

Let A and B are fuzzy ideals of R , then $A \cap B, A + B$ are fuzzy ideals of R , ([7],[8]).

Moreover, if $A(0) = B(0)$, then $A, B \subseteq A + B$. Also $A + A = A$ [9].

Now, we give definition and some properties of quotient fuzzy ring.

DEFINITION 1.1 [7]:

Let X is a fuzzy ring of R and A is a fuzzy ideal in X .

Define $X/A : R/A^* \rightarrow [0,1]$ such that :

$$X/A(a + A^*) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } a \in A^* \\ \sup \{ X(a + b) \} & \text{if } a \notin A^*, b \in A^* \end{cases}$$

For all $a + A^* \in R/A^*$, X/A is called a **quotient fuzzy ring of X by A** .

PROPOSITION 1.2 [6]:

Let X be a fuzzy ring of R and A is a fuzzy ideal in X , then X / A is a fuzzy ring of R / A^* .

PROPOSITION 1.3 [7]:

Let X be a fuzzy ring of R and A is a fuzzy ideal in X , then $X / A (0 + A^*)=1, [0 + A^* = A^*]$.

Now , we give definition and some properties of fuzzy external direct sum .

DEFINITION 1.1 [7]:

Let X be a fuzzy ring of R_1 and Y be a fuzzy ring of R_2 . Let $f : R_1 \oplus R_2 \rightarrow [0,1]$ definite by $T(a ,b) = \min \{X(a),Y(b)\}$ for all $(a ,b) \in R_1 \oplus R_2$. T is called **a fuzzy external direct sum of denoted by $X \oplus Y$** .

PROPOSITION 1.2 [7]:

If X and Y are fuzzy rings of R_1 and R_2 respectively ,then $T = X \oplus Y$ is a fuzzy ring of $R_1 \oplus R_2$.

PROPOSITION 1.3 [7]:

If X and Y are fuzzy rings of R_1 and R_2 respectively ,then $T = X \oplus Y$ is a fuzzy ring of $R_1 \oplus R_2$. A be a fuzzy ideal of R_1 such that $A \subseteq X$ and B be a fuzzy ideal of R_2 such that $B \subseteq Y$.Then :

- 1- $A \oplus B$ is a fuzzy ideal of $R_1 \oplus R_2$.
- 2- $(A \oplus B)_t = A_t \oplus B_t$ for all $t \in (0, (A \oplus B)(0 ,0)]$.
- 3- $A \oplus B$ is a fuzzy ideal of T , such that $(A \oplus B) \subseteq (X \oplus Y) = T$, where $(A \oplus B)(a ,b) = \min \{A(a),B(b)\}$, for all $(a ,b) \in R_1 \oplus R_2$.

PROPOSITION 1.4 [7]:

If X and Y are fuzzy rings of R_1 and R_2 respectively such that $T = X \oplus Y$. If A is a fuzzy ideal of $R_1 \oplus R_2$ such that $A \subseteq T$, then there exists B_1 and B_2 fuzzy ideals of R_1 and R_2 respectively such that $B_1 \subseteq X$ and $B_2 \subseteq Y$ and $A = B_1 \oplus B_2$.

COROLLARY 1.5 [7]:

If X and Y are fuzzy rings of R_1 and R_2 respectively. If A, C are fuzzy ideals of X and B, D are fuzzy ideals of Y . Then $A \oplus B = C \oplus D$ if and only if $A = C, B = D$.

We give some result about the Annihilator of fuzzy ideal.

DEFINITION 1.6 [7]:

Let A be a nonempty fuzzy ideal of R . **The Annihilator of A** denoted by $(F\text{-Ann } A)$ is defined by $\{x_t: x \in R, x_t \circ A \subseteq 0_1\}, t \in [0, A(0)]$.

Note that $(F\text{-Ann } A)(a) = \sup \{t: t \in [0, A(0)], a_t \circ A \subseteq 0_1\}, a \in R$.

PROPOSITION 1.7 [7]:

Let A be a fuzzy ideal of R , then $\text{Im}(F\text{-Ann } A) \subseteq \{0, A(0)\}$. That is $(\text{Im}(F\text{-Ann } A)) \leq 2$.

PROPOSITION 1.8 [7]:

Let X be fuzzy ring of R and $a \in R, [F\text{-Ann}(a_t)]^k = \text{ann}(a)$ for all $t, k \in (0, X(0)]$.

PROPOSITION 1.9 [10]:

Let X be a fuzzy ring of R and $a \in R, t \in [0, X(0)]$, then :

$F\text{-Ann}(a_t)$ is a fuzzy ideal of a fuzzy ring X of a ring R , when $F\text{-Ann}(a_t) \subseteq X$.

PROPOSITION 1.10 [7]:

1- Let A be a fuzzy ideal of R . Then $A \subseteq F\text{-Ann } \text{Ann } A$.

2- Let A and B be two fuzzy ideals of R such that $A(0) = B(0)$. Then

$$(F\text{-Ann } A) \cap (F\text{-Ann } B) = F\text{-Ann } (A+B).$$

3- Let A and B be two fuzzy ideals of R . Then $(F\text{-Ann } A) + (F\text{-Ann } B) \subseteq$

$$F\text{-Ann } (A \cap B).$$

We give some result about the Annihilator fuzzy ideal.

DEFINITION 1.11 [9]:

Let A be a nonempty fuzzy ideal of a ring R . A is called an **Annihilator fuzzy ideal** if and only if $A = F\text{-Ann Ann } A$.

PROPOSITION 1.14 [9]:

Let A be an Annihilator fuzzy ideal of R , then $| \text{Im}(A) | \leq 2$. That is $\text{Im}(A) \subseteq \{0, A(0)\}$.

PROPOSITION 1.15 [9]:

Let A be an Annihilator fuzzy ideal of R . Then: A_t is an annihilator ideal of R for all $t \in [0, A(0)]$.

PROPOSITION 1.16 [9]:

Let A and B be two Annihilator fuzzy ideals of a ring R . If $F\text{-Ann } A = F\text{-Ann } B$, then $A = B$.

PROPOSITION 1.17 [9]:

Let I be an ideal of a ring R and J be a fuzzy ideal of R which defined by :

$$J(x) = \begin{cases} c & \text{if } x \in I \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

for some $c \in (0, 1]$. Then I is an annihilator if and only if J is an Annihilator fuzzy ideal.

PROPOSITION 1.18 [10]:

Let A be an Annihilator fuzzy ideal of a ring R , then $(F\text{-Ann } A)_t = \text{ann } A_t$, $t \in [0, 1]$.

PROPOSITION 1.19 [10]:

Let A and B be two Annihilator fuzzy ideals of a ring R , then :

- 1) $(A \cap B)_t = A_t \cap B_t$, $t \in [0, 1]$.
- 2) $(A + B)_t = A_t + B_t$, $t \in [0, 1]$.
- 3) $[(F\text{-Ann } A)_t + (F\text{-Ann } B)_t] = \text{ann } A_t + \text{ann } B_t$, $t \in [0, 1]$.

PROPOSITION 1.20 [10]:

The Annihilator of a fuzzy ideal A of R ($F\text{-Ann } A$) is a fuzzy ideal of R .

We give some properties which we will be used in next sections.

PROPOSITION 1.21 [10]:

Let $X : R \rightarrow [0,1]$, $Y : R' \rightarrow [0,1]$ are fuzzy rings $f : R \rightarrow R'$ be homomorphism between them

and $A : R \rightarrow [0,1]$ a fuzzy ideal of X , $B : R' \rightarrow [0,1]$ a fuzzy ideal of Y , then

1. $f(A)$ is a fuzzy ideal of Y .
2. $f^{-1}(B)$ is a fuzzy ideal of X .

PROPOSITION 1.8 :

Let A and B be two fuzzy subsets of a ring R and f is inverse image function of B . Then :

- 1- $f(A) \cap f(B) = f(A \cap B)$.
- 2- $f(A) \circ f(B) = f(A \circ B)$.
- 3- $f(A_t) = (f(A))_t$.
- 4- $f^{-1}(A_t) = (f^{-1}(A))_t$.

PROOF :

To prove number one, let $x \in R$, $f(A \cap B)(x) = f[(A \cap B)(x)]$
 $= f[\min \{A(x), B(x)\}] = \min \{f(A(x)), f(B(x))\} = f(A) \cap f(B)$.

To prove number two, let $x \in R$, $f(A \circ B)(x) = f[(A \circ B)(x)]$
 $= f[\sup \{\min \{A(y), B(z)\} \mid x=y \cdot z\}]$, $y, z \in R$
 $= \sup \{\min \{f(A)(y), f(B)(z)\} \mid x=y \cdot z\} = [f(A) \circ f(B)](x)$.

Hence, $f(A) \circ f(B) = f(A \circ B)$.

Note that $A(f^{-1}(x)) = f(A(x))$ and $A(f(x)) = f^{-1}(A(x))$.

To prove number three, let $x \in f(A_t) \Leftrightarrow f^{-1}(x) \in A_t \Leftrightarrow A(f^{-1}(x)) \geq t \Leftrightarrow f(A(x)) \geq t \Leftrightarrow x \in (f(A))_t$.

To prove number four , let $x \in f^{-1} (A_t) \Leftrightarrow f(x) \in A_t \Leftrightarrow A(f(x)) \geq t \Leftrightarrow f^{-1} (A(x)) \geq t \Leftrightarrow x \in (f^{-1} (A))_t$.

PROPOSITION 1. 23 :

Let A and B be two fuzzy subsets of a ring R .Then :

- 1- $A \circ B \subseteq A \cap B$.
- 2- $(A \circ B)_t = A_t \cdot B_t$, $t \in [0,1]$.
- 3- $(A \cap B)_t = A_t \cap B_t$, $t \in [0,1]$.

PROOF :

To prove number one , let $x \in R$,

$$\begin{aligned} (A \circ B) (x) &= \sup \{ \min \{A(y),B(z)\} \mid x=y \cdot z \} \quad y , z \in R \\ &= \sup \{ \min \{A(x),B(1)\}, \min \{B(x),A(1)\}, \{ \min \{A(y),B(z)\} \mid x=y \cdot z \} \} \\ &\leq \min \{ \max \{A(x),B(x)\}, \max \{A(1),B(1)\}, \min \{A(y),B(z)\} \mid x=y \cdot z \} \\ &\leq \min \{ \min \{A(x),B(x)\}, \min \{A(1),B(1)\}, \min \{A(y),B(z)\} \mid x=y \cdot z \} \\ &\leq \min \{A(x),B(x)\} \\ &=(A \cap B) (x) \end{aligned}$$

Hence $A \circ B \subseteq A \cap B$.

To prove number there , since $A_t = \{x : x \in R \mid A(x) \geq t \}$, $B_t = \{x : x \in R \mid B(x) \geq t \}$.

$$\begin{aligned} (A \cap B)_t &= \{x : x \in R \mid (A \cap B)(x) \geq t \} . \\ &= \{x : x \in R \mid \min \{A(x),B(x)\} \geq t \} . \\ &= \{x : x \in R \mid A(x) \geq t, B(x) \geq t \} . \\ &= \min \{ \{x : x \in R \mid A(x) \geq t \}, \{x : x \in R \mid B(x) \geq t \} \} . = A_t \cap B_t . \end{aligned}$$

Hence $(A \cap B)_t = A_t \cap B_t$, $t \in [0,1]$.

PROPOSITION 1.24 :

Let X be a fuzzy ring of R and A be a fuzzy ideal of X .Then :

1- $x_t + A^* = (x + A^*)_t$, $x_t \subseteq X$.

2- $a_t + A^* \subseteq b_k + A^* \Leftrightarrow a_t \subseteq b_k$, $a_t, b_k \subseteq X$.

Proof :

1- Since $A_t = \{x : x \in R \mid A(x) \geq t\}$ and $A^* = \{x : x \in R \mid A(x) = A(0)\}$, implies that $(A^*)_t = \{x : x \in R \mid A(x) = A(0) \geq t\} = \{x : x \in R \mid A(x) = A(0)\} = A^*$.

Then $x_t + A^* = x_t + (A^*)_t$.

2- It is easy .

PROPOSITION 1.25 :

Let X be a fuzzy ring of R and A, B, C be fuzzy ideals of X . Then :

1- $(A \cap B) / C = (A / C) \cap (B / C)$.

2- $(A \circ B) / C = (A / C) \circ (B / C)$.

Proof :

1- Let $a + C^* \in R / C^*$,

$$[(A \cap B) / C](a + C^*) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } a \in C^* \\ \sup\{A \cap B(a + b)\} & \text{if } a \notin C^*, b \in C^* \end{cases}$$

$$= \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } a \in C^* \\ \sup\{\min A \rightrightarrows (a + b), B(a + b)\} & \text{if } a \notin C^*, b \in C^* \end{cases} \text{---(1)} .$$

$$[(A / C) \cap (B / C)](a + C^*) = \min\{A / C(a + C^*), B / C(a + C^*)\}$$

$$= \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } a \in C^* \\ \min\{\sup\{A(a + b), B(a + b)\} & \text{if } a \notin C^*, b \in C^* \end{cases}$$

$$= \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } a \in C^* \\ \sup\{\min A \rightrightarrows (a + b), B(a + b)\} & \text{if } a \notin C^*, b \in C^* \end{cases} \text{---(2)}$$

From (1) and (2) , $(A \cap B) / C = (A / C) \cap (B / C)$.

2- Let $a + C^* \in \mathbb{R} / C^*$,

$$[(A \circ B)/C](a + C^*) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } a \in C^* \\ \sup\{A \circ B(a + b)\} & \text{if } a \notin C^*, b \in C^* \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$[(A / C) \circ (B / C)](a + C^*) = \sup \{ \inf \{ \min \{ A / C(d_i + C^*), B / C(e_i + C^*) \} \mid d, e \in \mathbb{R} \} \mid a + C^* = \sum_{i=1}^n (d_i + C^*)(e_i + C^*) \} .$$

$$[(A / C) \circ (B / C)](a + C^*) = \sup \{ \inf \{ \min \{ A / C(d_i + C^*), B / C(e_i + C^*) \} \mid d, e \in \mathbb{R} \} \mid a + C^* = \sum_{i=1}^n (d_i e_i + C^*) \} .$$

But

$$(A / C)(d_i + C^*) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } d_i \in C^* \\ \sup\{\min A(di + b)\} & \text{if } d_i \notin C^*, b \in C^* \end{cases}$$

$$(B / C)(e_i + C^*) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } e_i \in C^* \\ \sup\{\min B(ei + b)\} & \text{if } e_i \notin C^*, b \in C^* \end{cases}$$

$$\text{Thus } [(A / C) \circ (B / C)](a + C^*) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } d_i \in C^* \text{ or } e_i \in C^* \\ \sup\{\inf\{\min\{\sup\{A(di + b)\}, \sup\{B(ei + b)\}\}\}\} & \text{if } d_i \text{ and } e_i \notin C^*, b \in C^* \end{cases}$$

$$= \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } d_i \in C^* \text{ or } e_i \in C^* \\ \sup\{\inf\{\min\{\sup\{A(di + b)\}, \sup\{B(ei + b)\}\}\}\} & \text{if } d_i \text{ and } e_i \notin C^*, b \in C^*, a = \sum_{i=1}^n d_i e_i \end{cases}$$

$$= \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } d_i \in C^* \text{ or } e_i \in C^* \\ \sup\{A \circ B(\sum_{i=1}^n (di + b)(ei + b))\} & \text{if } d_i \text{ and } e_i \notin C^*, b \in C^*, a = \sum_{i=1}^n d_i e_i \end{cases}$$

$$= \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } a \in C^* \\ \sup\{A \circ B[\sum_{i=1}^n d_i e_i + b \sum_{i=1}^n d_i + b \sum_{i=1}^n e_i + \frac{2}{b}]\} & \text{if } a \notin C^*, b \in C^* \end{cases}$$

$$= \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } a \in C^* \\ \sup\{A \circ B(a + b)\} & \text{if } a \notin C^*, b \in C^* \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

From (1) and (2), $(A \circ B) / C = (A / B) \circ (B / C)$.

PROPOSITION 1.26 :

Let X be fuzzy ring of R and $a \in R$, $[F\text{-Ann}(a_t)]^k = \text{ann}(a)$ for all $t, k \in (0, X(0)]$.

Proof :

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Let } x \in [F\text{-Ann}(a_t)]^k &\Leftrightarrow x_k \subseteq F\text{-Ann}(a_t) \\ &\Leftrightarrow x_k a_t \subseteq 0_{X(0)} \\ &\Leftrightarrow x a = 0 \\ &\Leftrightarrow x \in \text{ann}(a). \end{aligned}$$

PROPOSITION 1.27 :

$F\text{-Ann}(a_t)$ is a fuzzy ideal of a fuzzy ring X of a ring R , when $F\text{-Ann}(a_t) \subseteq X$.

Proof :

Let $b, c \in R$, to prove the following :

- 1- $F\text{-Ann}(a_t)(b-c) \geq \min \{ F\text{-Ann}(a_t)(b), F\text{-Ann}(a_t)(c) \}$.
- 2- $F\text{-Ann}(a_t)(bc) \geq \min \{ \max \{ F\text{-Ann}(a_t)(b), F\text{-Ann}(a_t)(c) \}, X(bc) \}$.

Now, let $F\text{-Ann}(a_t)(b) = h$ and $F\text{-Ann}(a_t)(c) = k$, where $h, k \in (0, X(0)]$.

Let $F\text{-Ann}(a_t)(b-c) = r$, to prove $r \geq \min \{ h, k \} = \lambda$.

Since $b_h a_t \subseteq 0_{X(0)}$ and $c_k a_t \subseteq 0_{X(0)}$ and $b_h \subseteq b_\lambda, c_k \subseteq c_\lambda$, then $b_\lambda a_t \subseteq b_h a_t, c_\lambda a_t \subseteq c_k a_t$

a_t , [9], implies that $b_\lambda a_t \subseteq 0_{X(0)}$, $c_\lambda a_t \subseteq 0_{X(0)}$, [9].

Hence $(b_\lambda a_t) - (c_\lambda a_t) \subseteq 0_{X(0)} - 0_{X(0)} = 0_{X(0)}$, [9], implies that $(b_\lambda - c_\lambda) a_t \subseteq 0_{X(0)}$ and $(b - c)_\lambda a_t \subseteq 0_{X(0)}$. Then $(b - c)_\lambda \subseteq F\text{-Ann}(a_t)$.

But $F\text{-Ann}(a_t)(b-c) = \sup \{ \beta: \beta \in (0, X(0)) \}$, $(b-c)_\beta a_t \subseteq 0_{X(0)} \} = r \geq \lambda$.

The first condition is true.

Now, to prove the second condition. Let $F\text{-Ann}(a_t)(bc) = r$ and $X(bc) = q$.

To prove $r \geq \min\{\max\{h, k\}, q\}$. Suppose that $\max\{h, k\} = h$, $(bc)_r a_t \subseteq 0_{X(0)}$

But $(bc)_h a_t \subseteq ((bc)_\lambda a)_\lambda \subseteq (c(ba))_\lambda \subseteq (c_h(b_h a_t)) \subseteq c_h 0_{X(0)} = 0_{X(0)}$ where $\lambda = \min\{h, t\}$. Since $F\text{-Ann}(a_t)(bc) = \sup \{ \beta: \beta \in (0, X(0)) \}$, $(bc)_\beta a_t \subseteq 0_{X(0)} \} = r \geq h$.

Similarly, if $\max\{h, k\} = k$, then $r \geq k$.

Hence $r \geq \max\{h, k\}$, then $F\text{-Ann}(a_t)$ is a fuzzy ideal of R .

Since $F\text{-Ann}(a_t)(bc) \subseteq X(bc)$, then $F\text{-Ann}(a_t)(bc) \geq \min\{\max\{F\text{-Ann}(a_t)(b), F\text{-Ann}(a_t)(c)\}, X(bc)\}$.

Thus $F\text{-Ann}(a_t)$ is a fuzzy ideal of a fuzzy ring X of a ring R .

S . 2 T-pure Fuzzy Ideal

In this section, we define a t-pure fuzzy ideal and we give some properties about it.

DEFINITION 2.1 :

A fuzzy ideal A of a fuzzy ring X of R is called t- pure fuzzy ideal of X if $A \cap B = A \circ B$ ($A \circ B = AB$) for each fuzzy ideal B of X .

Now, we give the following properties.

PROPOSITION 2.2 :

Let X be a fuzzy ring of R . $0_{X(0)}$ is a t-pure fuzzy ideal of X .

Proof :

For each a fuzzy ideal of X , to prove $0_{X(0)} \cap A = 0_{X(0)} \circ A$.

Ratio mathematica 18
(2008), 133 - 152

Let $a_t \subseteq (0_{X(0)} \cap A) \Rightarrow a_t \subseteq 0_{X(0)}$ and $a_t \subseteq A \Rightarrow 0_{X(0)}(a) \geq t$ and $A(a) \geq t$.

$$\text{But } 0_{X(0)}(a) = \begin{cases} X(0) & \text{if } a = 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } a \neq 0 \end{cases}$$

,then $X(0) \geq t \Rightarrow a=0. \Rightarrow a_t = 0_t$, but $(0_{X(0)} \circ A)(0) \geq t$. Thus $a_t = 0_t \subseteq (0_{X(0)} \cap A)$.

Hence $0_{X(0)}$ is a t -pure fuzzy ideal of X .

PROPOSITION 2.3 :

Let X be a fuzzy ring of R such that $X(0) = 1$, for all $a \in R$ and let I be ideal of R . I is t -pure ideal of $R \Leftrightarrow A(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \in I \\ c & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$ is a t -pure fuzzy ideal of X , when $c \in (0, X(0)]$.

Proof :

If I is t -pure ideal of R , to prove A is t -pure fuzzy ideal of X . A is a fuzzy ideal of X by [12].

But $A_t = I$ for all $t > c$ is a t -pure ideal of $R = X_t$ and $A_t = R$ for all $t \in (0, c]$ is t -pure ideal of $X_t = R$. Hence A_t is t -pure ideal for all $t \in (0, 1]$.

Then A is t -pure fuzzy ideal of X by [10].

Conversely, if A is t -pure fuzzy ideal of X , to prove I is t -pure ideal of R . Since A is t -pure fuzzy ideal of $X \Rightarrow A_t$ is a t -pure ideal of $R = X_t$ for all $t > 0$.

Then A_t is t -pure ideal of R for all $t > c$. Hence I is t -pure ideal of R .

PROPOSITION 2.4 :

Let X be a fuzzy ring of R and A is a fuzzy ideal of X . X is a t -pure fuzzy ring, then A is a t -pure fuzzy ideal.

PROOF :

The proof is similarly.

PROPOSITION 2.5 :

Let A be a fuzzy ideal of R . Then A is a t -pure fuzzy ideal if and only if A_t is a t -pure ideal of R , for all $t \in (0, A(0)]$.

PROOF :

Suppose A is a t -pure fuzzy ideal of R . To prove A_t is a t -pure ideal of R , for all $t \in (0, A(0)]$.

We must show that $A_t \cap I = A_t \cdot I$, for any ideal I of R .

Let $B : R \rightarrow [0, 1]$ defined by $B(x) = 1$ if $x \in I$, $B(x) = 0$ otherwise.

It can be easily shown that B is a fuzzy ideal of R and $I = (B)_t$, for all $t \in (0, A(0)]$. However $A \cap B = A \circ B$, since A is a t -pure fuzzy ideal of R .

Hence $(A \cap B)_t = (A \circ B)_t$, for all $t \in (0, A(0)]$. But $(A \cap B)_t = A_t \cap B_t = A_t \cap I$. And $(A \circ B)_t = A_t \cdot B_t$, by lemma (2.1) $= A_t \cdot I$, by [9].

Thus $A_t \cap I = A_t \cdot I$ and so A_t is a t -pure ideal of R , for all $t \in (0, A(0)]$.

Conversely, if A_t is a t -pure ideal of R , for all $t \in (0, A(0)]$. To prove A is a t -pure fuzzy ideal of R .

Let B be any fuzzy ideal of R , then B_t is a ideal of R , for all $t \in (0, A(0)]$ and so $A_t \cap B_t = A_t \cdot B_t$. Hence $(A \cap B)_t = A_t \cdot B_t$ and $A_t \cdot B_t = (A \circ B)_t$, for all $t \in (0, A(0)]$, by lemma (2.1).

Thus $(A \cap B)_t = (A \circ B)_t$, for all $t \in (0, A(0)]$, which implies $A \cap B = A \circ B$. Therefore A is a t -pure fuzzy ideal of R .

COROLLARY 2.6 :

Let I be an ideal of R . Then I is a t -pure ideal if and only if B is a t -pure fuzzy ideal of R where $B(x) = 1$ if $x \in I$ and $B(x) = 0$ otherwise.

PROOF :

It follows directly by proposition (2.3) and in fact $B_t = I$, for all $t \in [0, B(0)]$

PROPOSITION 2.7 [10]:

Let X and Y be fuzzy rings of R_1 and R_2 respectively and A and C be fuzzy ideals of X and B and D be fuzzy ideals of Y respectively. Then:

$$1- (A \oplus B) \cap (C \oplus D) = (A \cap C) \oplus (B \cap D).$$

$$2- (A \oplus B) \circ (C \oplus D) = (A \circ C) \oplus (B \circ D).$$

PROPOSITION 2.8 :

Let X and Y be fuzzy rings of R_1 and R_2 respectively and A and B be fuzzy ideals of X and Y respectively . Then A and B are t -pure fuzzy ideals of R_1 and R_2 respectively If and only if $A \oplus B$ is t -pure fuzzy ideal of $X \oplus Y$.

Proof :

Let $C \oplus D$ be any fuzzy ideal of $X \oplus Y$.

We must prove $(A \oplus B) \cap (C \oplus D) = (A \oplus B) \circ (C \oplus D)$.

It is enough to prove $(A \oplus B) \cap (C \oplus D) \subseteq (A \oplus B) \circ (C \oplus D)$.

But C is a fuzzy ideal of X and D is a fuzzy ideal of $Y \Rightarrow A \cap C = A \circ C$ and $B \cap D = B \circ D$.

$(A \oplus B) \cap (C \oplus D) = (A \cap C) \oplus (B \cap D)$ by proposition (2.4 ,2) .

$= (A \circ C) \oplus (B \circ D)$ by define (2.1)

$\subseteq (A \oplus B) \circ (C \oplus D)$ by proposition (2.4 ,1) .

Hence $A \oplus B$ is t -pure fuzzy ideal of $X \oplus Y$.

Conversely ,to prove A and B are t -pure fuzzy ideals of X and Y respectively.

Let C be any fuzzy ideal of X and D be any fuzzy ideal of Y .

To prove $A \circ C = A \cap C$ and $B \circ D = B \cap D$.

But $(A \oplus B) \cap (C \oplus D) = (A \oplus B) \circ (C \oplus D)$.

Since $(A \oplus B)$, $(C \oplus D)$ are fuzzy ideals of $X \oplus Y$ and $(A \oplus B)$ is t -pure fuzzy ideal of $X \oplus Y$.

Note $(A \oplus B) \cap (C \oplus D) = (A \cap C) \oplus (B \cap D)$ by proposition (2.4 ,2) and $(A \oplus B) \cap (C \oplus D) = (A \circ C) \oplus (B \circ D)$ by define (2.1) .

Thus $(A \circ C) \oplus (B \circ D) = (A \cap C) \oplus (B \cap D) \Rightarrow A \circ C = A \cap C$ and $B \circ D = B \cap D$. Hence A and B are t -pure fuzzy ideals of X and Y respectively .

PROPOSITION 2.9 :

Let $X : R_1 \rightarrow [0,1]$, $Y : R_2 \rightarrow [0,1]$ are fuzzy rings $f : R_1 \rightarrow R_2$ be homomorphism function between them and onto and $A : R_1 \rightarrow [0,1]$ is a fuzzy ideal of R_1 and $B : R_2 \rightarrow [0,1]$ is a fuzzy ideal of Y , then :

1. If A is t -pure fuzzy ideal of R_1 , then $f(A)$ is t -pure fuzzy ideal of R_2 .
2. If B is t -pure fuzzy ideal of R_2 , then $f^{-1}(B)$ is t -pure fuzzy ideal of R_1 .

PROOF:

To prove the first ,let C be fuzzy ideal of R_2 .To prove $f(A)$ is t -pure fuzzy ideal of R_2 ,that mean $f(A) \cap C = f(A) \circ C$.

It is enough prove $f(A) \cap C \subseteq f(A) \circ C$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Consider } f^{-1}(f(A) \cap C) &= f^{-1}(f(A)) \cap f^{-1}(C) \\ &= A \cap f^{-1}(C) \\ &= A \circ f^{-1}(C) , \text{ since } A \text{ is } t\text{-pure fuzzy ideal .} \end{aligned}$$

Hence $f[f^{-1}(f(A) \cap C)] = f[A \circ f^{-1}(C)]$

$$\begin{aligned} f(A) \cap C &= f(A) \circ f(f^{-1}(C)) \\ f(A) \cap C &= f(A) \circ C \end{aligned}$$

Then $f(A)$ is t -pure fuzzy ideal of R_2 .

To prove the second ,let D be fuzzy ideal of R_1 .To prove $f^{-1}(B)$ is t -pure fuzzy ideal of R_1 ,that mean $f^{-1}(B) \cap D = f^{-1}(B) \circ D$.

It is enough prove $f^{-1}(B) \cap D \subseteq f^{-1}(B) \circ D$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Consider } f(f^{-1}(B) \cap D) &= f(f^{-1}(B)) \cap f(D) \\ &= B \cap f(D) \\ &= B \circ f(D) , \text{ since } B \text{ is } t\text{-pure fuzzy ideal .} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Hence } f^{-1} [f(f^{-1}(B) \cap D)] &= f^{-1} [B \circ f^{-1}(D)] \\ f^{-1}(B) \cap D &= f^{-1}(B) \circ f^{-1}(f(D)) \\ f^{-1}(B) \cap C &= f^{-1}(B) \circ D \end{aligned}$$

Then $f^{-1}(B)$ is t-pure fuzzy ideal of R_1 .

COROLLARY 2.10 :

Let $X : R_1 \rightarrow [0,1]$, $Y : R_2 \rightarrow [0,1]$ are fuzzy rings $f : R_1 \rightarrow R_2$ be homomorphism function between them and onto and $A : R_1 \rightarrow [0,1]$ is a fuzzy ideal of X and $B : R_2 \rightarrow [0,1]$ is a fuzzy ideal of Y , then :

1. If A is t-pure fuzzy ideal of X , then $f(A)$ is t-pure fuzzy ideal of Y .
2. If B is t-pure fuzzy ideal of Y , then $f^{-1}(B)$ is t-pure fuzzy ideal of X .

PROPOSITION 2.11 :

Let X be a fuzzy ring of R . A , B and C are fuzzy ideals of X such that $A \subseteq B$. X/A is a fuzzy ring of R/A^* and B/A is a fuzzy ideal in X/A . B/A is a t-pure fuzzy ideal in X/A if and only if B is t-pure fuzzy ideal of X .

PROOF :

Suppose B/A is a t-pure fuzzy ideal in X/A , to prove B is t-pure fuzzy ideal of X .

Let C be fuzzy ideal of X , C/A is fuzzy ideal in X/A .

$(B/A) \cap (C/A) = (B/A) \circ (C/A)$ if and only if $(B \cap C)/A = (B \circ C)/A$ by proposition (1.14), proposition (2.8) if and only if $(B \cap C) = (B \circ C)$ by proposition (1.15). Then B is t-pure fuzzy ideal of X .

Conversely, if B is t-pure fuzzy ideal of X , to prove B/A is a t-pure fuzzy ideal in X/A .

Let C/A is fuzzy ideal in X/A , C be fuzzy ideal of X .

$$\begin{aligned} (B/A) \cap (C/A) &= (B \cap C)/A \text{ by proposition (1.14)} \\ &= (B \circ C)/A \text{ by definition (2.5).} \\ &= (B/A) \circ (C/A) \text{ by proposition (1.14).} \end{aligned}$$

Then B / A is a t -pure fuzzy ideal in X / A .

S.3 The Behavior of Fuzzy Ideals of Prime Fuzzy Ideal :

In this section ,we shall fuzzify this concept in to prime fuzzy ideal . We give some basic properties of this concept .

we shall study the concept in to weakly t -pure fuzzy ideal , we give some basic properties of this concept .

We shall study the relationships between prime fuzzy ideal , weakly t -pure fuzzy ideal and t -pure fuzzy ideal .

DEFINITION 3.1 [13] :

Let A be a fuzzy ideal of R .Then A is called a **prime fuzzy ideal of R** if either $A = \lambda_R$ or

- 1- A is not constant , and
- 2- For any fuzzy ideals B and C of R ,if $B \circ C \subseteq A$, then either $B \subseteq A$ or $C \subseteq A$.

PROPOSITION 3.2 [14] :

A fuzzy ideal X is a prime ideal if and only if 0_1 is a prime fuzzy ideal of X .

PROPOSITION 3.3 [14] :

If A is a prime fuzzy ideal ,then A_t is a prime ideal for all $t \in (0,1]$.

PROPOSITION 3.4 [14] :

The Annihilator fuzzy ideal A is a prime fuzzy ideal.

PROPOSITION 3.5 [14] :

If X is a prime fuzzy ring ,then $F\text{-Ann } A$ is a prime fuzzy ideal of R for every fuzzy ideal A of X .

REMARKS 3.6 [14] :

The converse of proposition (3.5) is not true in general , for example :

Let M be the Z -module $Z \oplus Z_2$ and let :

$$X(a, b) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } (a, b) \in 2Z \oplus Z_2 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$2_{1/2} (0,1)_{1/2} = (0,0)_{1/2} = (0,0)_1$.But $(0,0)_{1/2} \not\subseteq (0,0)_1$ and $2_{1/2} \not\subseteq ((0,0)_1 : X)$.

Hence X not prime fuzzy ideal .

However $F\text{-Ann } X = ((0,0)_1 : X)$. But $((0,0)_t : X_t) = ((0,0) : 2Z \oplus Z_2) = \{0\}$.

REMARK 3.7 :

Let X be a prime fuzzy ring of R and A be non empty fuzzy ideal of X , then A is not necessarily a prime ideal .For example shows.

EXAMPLE:

Let $X: Q \rightarrow [0,1]$ such that: $X(a) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } a \in Z \\ \frac{1}{2} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$

X is a fuzzy ring of Z and Let $A: Q \rightarrow [0,1]$ such that: $A(a) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } a \in 4Z \\ \frac{1}{2} & \text{if } a \in 2Z/4Z \\ \frac{1}{3} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$

A is a fuzzy ideal of X . However , $5_{0.4} (6/5) = 6_{0.4}$, but $6_{0.4} \not\subseteq A$. On the other hand , $(6/5)_{1/2} \not\subseteq A$, also $5_{0.4} \not\subseteq (A: X)$.

THEOREM 3.8 :

Let X be a prime fuzzy ring of R , then a proper fuzzy ideal A of X of R is a t-pure fuzzy ideal if and only if X is a t-pure fuzzy ring .

Proof :

Suppose A is a t-pure fuzzy ideal . Since A is prime fuzzy ideal by proposition (3.7) , then A_t is prime ideal in X_t for all $t \in (0,1]$,by [14] .

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